

Extended data: sample Narrative Policy Framework (NPF) codebook

The below table presents a sample codebook for applying the NPF methodology in the study "Capturing attention: media and institutional narratives on carbon capture, utilisation, and storage in three EU countries", which will be published on Open Research Europe. The sample codebook is based on Brumbaugh and Rupp, 2020.

Codebook elements	
Narrative number	
Date	
Date of publication	
Coder initials	
Link	
Author position	
Details/notes	
Stakeholder group authoring narrative	
Details	
If "other", please detail	
Document type	
If "other", please detail	
Core narrative elements	
Character: hero	
Please detail	
Character: villain	
Please detail	
Character: victim	
Please detail	
In what period is the narrative constructed?	
In what space is the narrative constructed?	
Plot: does it exist?	
Plot: what type? (option 1)	
Please detail	
Plot: what type? (option 2)	
Please detail	
Plot: what type? (option 3)	
Please detail	
Causal mechanism: does it exist?	
Causal mechanism: what type?	
Please detail	
Moral of the story: does the narrative offer a policy/technology solution?	
If yes, what is the solution?	

Is science or evidence cited in the narrative?	
If yes, what science is being used?	
What is it used for?	
If "other", please detail	
Is anything missing from the evidence cited?	
If "other", please detail	
Narrative strategies	
Costs (of proposed and opposed policy solutions)	
Does the narrative imply costs to the solution?	
If yes, what entities bear the costs?	
Are the costs concentrated or diffused?	
Benefits (of proposed and opposed policy solutions)	
Does the narrative imply benefits to the solution?	
If yes, what entities bear the benefits?	
Are the benefits concentrated or diffused?	
Policy stance adopted by the narrative	
Policy surrogate: does the narrative wrap an issue in larger normative issues?	
Does the policy stance use devil-shift?	
Does the policy stance use angel-shift?	
Can the policy stance be considered "extreme"? (e.g. CCUS as inevitable, CCUS as carbon lock-in)	

References

Brumbaugh, Amelia, and John A. Rupp. 2020. "Wabash CarbonSAFE Subtask 4.1 - Application of Policy Frameworks for Improved Carbon Capture and Storage Social Site Characterization & Stakeholder Engagement." DOE-FE0031626-2. Univ. of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, IL (United States). <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1664756>.